

Diversity and toxin production of cyanobacteria on Nantucket island

Pia H. Moisander

University of Massachusetts Dartmouth, Department of Biology, 285 Old Westport Road, North Dartmouth, MA 02747

Introduction

The main goal of this project was to investigate diversity of potentially toxic cyanobacteria on Nantucket Island. Previous studies have reported a range of cyanobacteria in blooms from the island, and some of these have been confirmed to be toxic (*Microcystis aeruginosa*). The goal of this study was to obtain information for other potential toxic species among the bloom formers, investigate the distribution of these species, and obtain phylogenetic information for these taxa. The study employed microscopic observations combined with toxin analyses and molecular investigations, with a specific focus on potential influence of elevated salinity on toxic blooms in the ponds on the island, some of which experience periodic flushing by ocean water. These results will be used as background information for future potential studies on cyanobacterial ecology on the island.

Materials and methods

Field survey

Samples were collected on Nantucket Island on August 4-6, 2011 (Figure 1). Sampling was conducted from a dock (station 9), from a small boat (stations 2-6) or from shoreline by wading (the rest of the stations).

Water samples were collected with a Wildco horizontal water sampler at ~0.5 m below the surface. Water was poured into an acid washed (10% HCl) and autoclaved

polycarbonate bottle that was stored chilled in a cooler. Temperature was recorded using a YSI probe. Back in the laboratory (UMB field station), subsamples were processed for determination of total and dissolved microcystin, microscopy, and DNA analyses. Salinity was recorded using a refractometer.

For total microcystin, a 10 mL aliquot was poured into a brown glass vial that was sealed with a serum stopper, then frozen at -20°C. For dissolved microcystin, a ~10 mL aliquot was filtered through GF/F filters, and the flow through was collected into brown glass vials that were sealed, then frozen at -20°C. The samples were transported frozen to UMass Dartmouth for further analyses. For measurement of microcystin, the samples thawed, then sonicated on ice using Fisher Scientific sonic dismembrator for 30 s at 23 kHz. Enviroligix 96-well QuantiPlate microcystin kit was used. The calibrator standards were run with each set of samples. The iMark™ Microplate Absorbance Reader 168-1130 by BioRad on a 450 nm setting was used to read the plate.

For determination of presence of anatoxin-a and saxitoxin, two total-toxin samples from the Hummock Pond were sent to analysis to the GreenWater laboratories (Florida). ELISA assay and LC/MS/MS was used to target a range of saxitoxins, and anatoxin-a was detected with LC/MS/MS.

For collection of DNA, 30 to 50 mL water was filtered on Supor 0.2 um pore size filters. Filters were folded and placed in sterile bead beater tubes that were immediately frozen in liquid nitrogen. Samples were transported to UMass Dartmouth for further analyses in a dry shipper. DNA was extracted using a modified Qiagen Plant kit protocol (Moisander et al. 2009). Polymerase chain reaction was conducted for samples from all sites to amplify *mcyA* or *cpcBA*. PCR conditions followed previous protocols (Moisander et al. 2009). Amplified products were cloned into *E. coli* in the pGEM-t vector, and plasmids purified with Millipore Montage 96-well system. Samples were sent to sequencing at the UMass Medical School sequencing center.

For microscopy, approximately 12 mL sample was transferred into a sterile polyethylene tube and Lugol's solution was added as a preservative to the appropriate coloration. Samples were observed with a Zeiss microscope and observed potential cyanobacterial toxin producers were recorded by microscopy.

Influence of salinity on toxin release

An experiment was conducted to investigate the influence of salinity on toxin distribution in the water. After microscopic investigations had revealed presence of *Microcystis* on Clark Cove, water was collected at this site for a salinity experiment. Water was transported to the UMB field station, where it was aliquoted into nine 500-mL polycarbonate bottles. Salinity treatments included 0, 9, and 18 g NaCl L⁻¹ final concentration (over the initial). Bottles were placed in a basket and incubated in the marsh immersed in seawater for 24 h. At the termination of the experiment, samples were collected for total and dissolved toxins (see above).

Results and Discussion

Temperature varied from 23.1 to 26.8 at the sites (Table 1). Salinity was 1-4 ppt at all other sites except the Long Pond and Sesacha Pond. Microscopic observations

showed the presence of *Anabaena* spp. in Hummock Pond and Maxey Pond, while *Microcystis* sp. was observed at one station only, Clark Cove (Table 1, Figure 2).

Table 1. Temperature, salinity and potentially toxic cyanobacterial taxa, if any, observed by microscopy.

Stn	Location	Temperature	Potentially toxic cyanobacteria observed by microscopy	Salinity	DNA sample # used for PCR
1	Sesacha Pond	24.3°C		15	1851
2	Head of Hummock	26.8°C		1	1839
3	Head of Hummock	25.2°C	<i>Anabaena</i>	1	1843
4	Opening behind Barlett Rd (Hummock)	25.6°C	<i>Anabaena</i>	3	1845
5	Northern end of opening (Hummock)	25°C	<i>Anabaena</i>	4	1847
6	Southern point of Hummock	26.5°C		4	1849
7	Clark Cove	25.8°C	<i>Microcystis</i>	4	1851
8	Maxey pond	23.1°C	<i>Anabaena</i>	2	1853
9	Long Pond	26.5°C		19	1855
10	Long Pond North side	24.3°C		18	1857
11	South end of Miacomet pond	24.6°C		3	1849
12	Mid Miacomet Pond	24.1°C		3	1861

The only site where total microcystin was detected was Clark Cove, where the concentration was 3.85 ppb. Microcystin in the dissolved fraction at this site, and all other sites, was 0 (or below detection). A low microcystin value of 0.06 ppb in the dissolved fraction was also detected at station 6, (Hummock Pond south) (Table 2). In the salinity experiment conducted with the Clark Cove water, there was a slight increase in total toxin concentration in response to salinity over the 24 h incubation period, and this increase was at the same level under 9 and 18 g NaCl L⁻¹ additions (Table 2, Figure 3). Dissolved microcystin increased approximately 2-3 -fold with an increase of the salinity to 9 g NaCl L⁻¹ (Table 2, Figure 3). All of the microcystin was in the dissolved fraction when the salinity increased to 18 g NaCl L⁻¹ (Table 2, Figure 3). The increase in dissolved microcystin suggests cell membrane integrity was compromised at the experimental salt concentrations, allowing toxin release. Such increases in the form of toxin may be important in predicting the ultimate fate of these toxins in estuaries. Total toxin in both of the salt treatments increased, and was at a comparable level, inspite the fact a smaller portion of total toxin was in the dissolved phase in the mid-salinity treatment. This suggests the toxin was stable in the dissolved phase for 24 h.

Figure 2. **A.** *Anabaena* from station 1. **B.** *Anabaena* from station 2. **C.** *Anabaena* from station 3. **D.** *Anabaena* from station 5. **E.** *Anabaena* from station 6. **F.** *Microcystis* from station 7. All figures were imaged under a 40x magnification.

Figure 3. Microcystin at the end of the salinity experiment. Panel on the left, total microcystin. Panel on the right, dissolved microcystin. Bar 1 is zero salinity, bar 2 is 9 g NaCl L⁻¹ (medium salt) and bar 3 is 18 g NaCl L⁻¹ (high salt).

The levels in the Clark Cove are greater than the The World Health Organization guideline for Microcystin-LR in drinking water (1 ppb), but less than the guideline for recreational waters (20 ppb).

Table 2. Concentration of microcystin in the salinity experiment.

Station	NaCl (L ⁻¹) added	Dissolved or Total	ppb
7	0	Total	3.85
7	0	Total	3.92
7	0	Total	3.07
7	9	Total	4.32
7	9	Total	4.83
7	9	Total	4.90
7	18	Total	4.58
7	18	Total	4.44
7	18	Total	4.36
7	0	Dissolved	0
7	0	Dissolved	0.54
7	0	Dissolved	0.38
7	9	Dissolved	0.95
7	9	Dissolved	1.25
7	9	Dissolved	0.92
7	18	Dissolved	4.60
7	18	Dissolved	4.68
7	18	Dissolved	4.54

Anatoxin-a and saxitoxin concentrations were measured in GreenWater labs (Florida) for two samples collected from the Hummock Pond (Stations 3 and 4). Neither toxin was detected in these samples, suggesting these *Anabaena* spp. on Nantucket are not toxin producing variants.

Polymerase chain reaction resulted in bands for *cpcBA* from most stations (Figure 4), while *mcyA* was detected only at Clark Cove (Figure 5). The sequences obtained were compared against the NCBI database using BLAST searches (Table 3). The sequence quality from UMass Worcester was lower than expected, and the reads recovered were more limited than what was submitted to the center. The sequences show the sample from Clark Cove was confirmed to be *Microcystis aeruginosa*. Two *Anabaena* spp. were recorded in the community. At one of the sites, all repeats of the *cpcBA* were from a cyanobacterium that had the closest identity with *Synechocystis* – although this identity was only 88% at the DNA level. The sequences have been submitted to GenBank.

Figure 4. Gel electrophoresis of PCR using *cpcBA* primers. Samples 1849, 1845, 1843, 1835, a negative control, and Fermentas 100 pb DNA ladder are shown. Samples were loaded on two wells each.

Figure 5. Gel electrophoresis of PCR with *mcyA* primers. Samples 1851, 1847, 1845, 1843, a negative control, and 100 bp DNA size marker are shown. Samples were loaded on two wells each. Clark's Cove sample was the only one that amplified.

Table 3. BLAST results for sequences recovered. GenBank accession numbers are shown for the closest cultivated relatives. Sequences M1835CC_C, M1839CC_C, M1845CC_C, and M1851FF_C have been submitted to GenBank.

Sample ID	Target gene	Closest cultivated relative in NCBI	% identity	Query coverage
M1835CC_C	<i>cpcBA</i>	<i>Synechocystis</i> AJ003180.1	88%	99%
M1839CC_C	<i>cpcBA</i>	<i>Anabaena bergii</i> GU197697.1	95%	99%
		<i>Aphanizomenon issatschenkoi</i> FN552374.1	95%	99%
M1843CC_C	<i>cpcBA</i>	<i>Anabaena oumiana</i> GU197689.1	100%	99%
		+several other <i>Anabaena</i> spp. (sequence too short for submission)		
M1845CC_C	<i>cpcBA</i>	<i>Anabaena oumiana</i> GU197689.1	98%	100%
M1851FF_01	<i>mcyA</i>	<i>Microcystis aeruginosa</i> EU203572.1	99%	100%

Acknowledgment of your message: Sequence submission

Please do not reply <nobody@ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>
To: Pia Moisander <pmoisander@umassd.edu>

Sun, Apr 29, 2012 at 9:09 PM

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References:

Moisander PH, Lehman P, Ochiai M, Lincoff A, Corum S. 2009. Diversity of *Microcystis aeruginosa* in the Klamath River and San Francisco Bay delta, California, USA. *Aquat. Micr. Ecol.* **57**: 19-31